

DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED IN THE PROCESS OF SENTENCE FORMATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article is about correcting the mistakes in sentence structure that cause many difficulties among English language learners. English sentence construction presents a number of difficulties for both language learners and writers. The complex rules governing word order, phrase construction, and sentence formation pose a significant challenge for learners of syntax. To overcome these obstacles, one must be highly proficient in the language, have a thorough grasp of English sentence structure standards, and practise a lot.

Key words: syntax, tense, word formation, hesitation, the formation of parts of speech, sentence types, sentence analysis, sentence comprehension.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/pberdp48>

All languages in the world are now being compared to English. For this reason, many English language learners have a lot of difficulty in following the rules of sentence formation in this language and being able to understand and apply it correctly, taking into account the increasing interest in learning this language. For example, the Uzbek language, like all other languages, has its own place in the correct construction of sentences and the construction of sentences in compliance with grammatical rules. It is natural that we encounter various differences when we compare the two languages. When we translate sentences, we understand how to make a sentence in English and whether or not it is compatible with Uzbek. The concept of constituency—many words functioning as one unit—must be understood in light of syntax. Constituency is required, especially when using sentence diagramming, to establish the hierarchy inside long and complex sentences. The position of the parts of the sentence is very important in the composition of the sentence. Take a look at the syntax examples below to make your own judgement. Observe how changing a single word alters the sentence's overall meaning. Remember that can only be an adverb or an adjective; adverbs can modify other adverbs or verbs, while adjectives can change the nouns that follow them.

Only Dildora speaks true.

Faqat Dildora haqiqatni gapiradi.

Meaning: Dildora is the only person who speaks true. No one except Dildora speaks true, not even parents.

Dildora only speaks true.

Dildora faqat haqiqatni gapiradi.

Meaning: Speaking true is the only thing Dildora does. She doesn't work, she doesn't play - speaking true is all she does. Only by changing the place of words, there is a change in the meaning of the sentence. Numerous instances of structural discordance caused by

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inversion. It is natural that in English sentences predicate comes after the subject. But in Uzbek language predicate comes at the ends of the sentence.

Example: I play with my cat –Men mushugim bilan o'ynayman.

Many learners do not use word formation correctly when making sentences. In a sentence or text, you have to change the form of a word, e.g. from a noun to an adjective, or from a verb to a noun. For example:

The _ was very clever. (work)

_juda aqlli edi. (ishlamoq)

You have to complete the sentence with the person noun (worker). You change the verb (work) into the person noun (worker). We can complete the Uzbek sentence with (ishchi). There is the verb (ishlamoq) changed into noun (ishchi).

Nouns often end: -ment, -ion, -ness, -ity.

People nouns often end: -er, -or, -ist, -ian.

Adjectives often end: -able, -ible, -ive, -al, -ic, -ed, -ing.

Some verbs end: -ise, -ate, -en.

Adverbs often end: -ly.

While different grammars have varied classifications for the parts of speech, the majority of conventional grammars list eight parts of speech in English: nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, and interjections. But in Uzbek language has six parts of speech: nouns, adverbs, pronouns, verbs, adjectives. Many words can function as different parts of speech depending on how they are used. For example, "PLAY" can be a noun (e.g., "I like your PLAY") or a verb (e.g., "don't PLAY"). But in Uzbek language we can make this word with the help of suffix. For example: "O'YIN" is a noun (Men O'YININGNI yaxshi ko'raman) "O'YNAMA" is a verb which was made by suffix. O'YIN+A=O'YINA here the word is missing one vowel due to inversion and adding the other suffix which made a verb.

To sum up, there are a number of reasons why learners of English may have trouble forming sentences, including grammatical requirements, vocabulary restrictions, pronunciation issues, and cultural differences. To overcome these barriers to successful communication, one must constantly practice, be exposed to situations, and get direction. Individual learning preferences and past language exposure may also have an impact on how simple or challenging it is to acquire English sentence structure.

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